

Clinical symptoms of menopause

Katarzyna Szymona-Pałkowska^{1A-F}, Jolanta Adamczuk^{2A-F}, Malwina Cypriańska^{3A-F}, Marta Sapalska^{4A-F}, Agnieszka Pedrycz^{5A-F}, Jacek Kraczkowski^{3A-F}

¹Department of Clinical Psychology, John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin (KUL), Poland

²Private practice, Nałęczów, Poland

³Department of Obstetrics and Pathology of Pregnancy, Medical University of Lublin, Lublin, Poland

⁴The Social Insurance Institution, Lublin, Poland

⁵Department of Histology and Embryology Medical University in Lublin, Poland

Received: April 11. 2017 Accepted: May 12. 2017

Abstract

Menopause, according to the definition of the World Health Organization (WHO), is defined as the last natural menstrual bleeding after cessation of which over the next 12 months do not already occurred subsequent bleeding.

Perimenopausal period is the last period of turbulent changes hormone. It is a transitional stage between the beginning of the reproductive period of aging women. It usually occurs between 44 and 55 years of life.

It is a natural process which is the result of a physiological blanking ovarian function and characterized by a number of disorders of psychic and somatic. Although perimenopause symptoms are experienced by most women, however, not the end, we are aware of the correlation between the perception of one's own body and the functioning of biopsychosocial during menopause.

The purpose of this study was the analysis of the clinical symptoms of menopause which is an integral part of the aging process, as well as its impact on quality of life of women.

Keywords: *menopause, menopause, quality of life*

Introduction

Menopause is natural biological process. During the period following the weakening of hormonal ovarian function there is a loss of the menstrual cycle. The period of transition stage between reproductive aging. Normal begins between 45 and 55 years of age. For many women, it is still time intensive, active work.

This is undoubtedly a difficult period in the life of every woman. Changes in the level of hormones contribute to the onset of symptoms of vegetative, somatic and psychiatric disorders which cause a number of ailments interfere with the joy of life.

Disorders associated with the process of menopause may be accompanied by a woman from a few to several years.

Imprint its mark on the quality of life, they determine the health as well as affect the quality of family and social relations.

Dysregulated endocrine system makes many women experience mood changes, tearfulness, memory

problems, depression has a tendency becomes more tense and nervous.

According Bręborowicz [1] climacteric syndrome is a syndrome of symptoms associated with the menopause process. For a woman it is a very difficult period and the leading problem is the team somatic symptoms. These include hot flashes, trouble sleeping, night sweats and headaches. These symptoms generally fall into vasomotor, somatic and psychological.

Perimenopausal period, according to recently proposed terminology called transition period, characterized by large fluctuations in hormone levels. Women report at that time varied symptoms symptoms, which may include vasomotor symptoms [2].

Vasomotor symptoms are among the most commonly reported symptoms of menopause, but their pathogenesis is not yet fully explained [3]. Are closely related to the functioning of the hypothalamus, as well as a sharp decrease in the concentration of estradiol [4].

The mechanism of thermoregulation also affect the serotonergic and noradrenergic. Also emphasizes the participation of opioid receptors, adrenal and autonomic nervous system [5].

According to Redberg [6] there is a correlation between of menopause symptoms of polymorphism of genes responsible for regulation within the functioning of sex hormones and a predisposition to the occurrence of vasomotor symptoms.

Hot flashes, night sweats, headaches apply 50-75% of women [7]. For most women, these symptoms occur 6-12 months before the onset of menopause will disappear in 2-3 years after its disappearance [1].

Vasomotor symptoms include upper half of the body including the face area, neck and chest. Accompanied by severe redness, sweating, feeling the viscosity of the skin, chills, anxiety, palpitations, difficulty remembering and concentrating [3,5].

They are perceived as burdensome, often interfere with normal sleep, in effect, contributing to the shortage of [8]. It is also believed that more frequent among women with in the past experienced premenstrual syndrome. The duration of menopausal symptoms is variable and can last from a few seconds to several minutes. Their intensity is under the action of heat or hot foods [3,9].

A significant role of stress as a factor having a large influence on the severity of vasomotor symptoms also emphasizes Thurston and others [10].

Among the factors that increase the likelihood of menopausal symptoms also awarded to ethnic and racial differences. According to Gold, and others [11], these symptoms most commonly reported by women of afro-American, Asian rarest while.

According to Crawford [12] the above treatment may be the result of a diet rich in soy products as well as differences in the perception of subjective symptoms.

The study, which conducted Thurston and others [13] highlighted the excess body fat as a predictor disrupts the physiological mechanisms of thermoregulation. It also stressed the endocrine character. In contrast, Freeman and others [14] a group of factors intensifying vasomotor symptoms have joined the low socio-economic status and smoking.

Research Crandall et al [15] found that the symptoms of menopause can decisively affected the health of women in the years to their lives. This deterioration may occur in the area of cardiovascular and skeletal system.

The time of menopause is also extensive changes within the urogenital. Urogenital atrophy and disorders of libido are inherent process accompanying the woman during this period.

According to current literature, statistical woman for more than one third of your life is experiencing the state

of relative hypoestrogenemia [16]. Urogenital atrophy involving the atrophic changes in the urogenital organ of the woman is a condition closely related to estrogen deficiency and is a condition experienced by women during menopause. This phenomenon is correlated with the dryness of vaginal mucosa and vulvar, vaginal discharge, pruritus, dyspareunia [17]. Atrophy of the epithelium lining the mucous membranes of the urogenital system contributes to the thinning. Observed changes in the vaginal mucosa. On the wall may appear slightly petechiae. The loss ripple and reduces the flexibility leads to a narrowing and shortening the organ. Within the labia major loss of subcutaneous adipose tissue, which in turn leads to the fusion of the labia minora, the narrowing of the vaginal opening [18].

As a result of cessation of estrogen stimulation is altered vaginal pH. Reducing the amount of lactic acid bacteria, thus shifting the pH to alkaline. In childbearing pH of the vagina are 3.5-4.5 and after menopause increases to 5.0 or more, contributing to an increased risk of infections of the genitourinary tract. Also reduced the amount of vaginal discharge, vaginal mucous membrane disappears, there are problems of a sexual nature - dyspareunia [19].

According to the North American Menopause Society [20] problems related to changes in the lining of the vagina growing, but partly disappear after treatment. Untreated decay mucosa intensifies the pain. Determines the quality of life, predisposing to the formation of petechiae, ulceration, cracking and bleeding.

According to Buster [21] for many women with the onset of menopause problems arise in the field on sexual life. Their essence is the loss of sexual desire resulting from a lack of sexual arousal, orgasm, pain during sexual intercourse (female sexual dysfunction, FSD).

The decline in estrogen levels is only indirectly contribute to the disorder in terms of sex life, but the whole process is determined by changes extending at neuroendocrine.

Produced by the ovaries and adrenal androgens (testosterone and androstenedione) provide well-being, they add strength and energy to work, a positive effect on sexual desire [22]. While the decline in the level of testosterone decreases interest in sex, deteriorating mood and self-esteem. Appears fatigue.

In women of childbearing age testosterone is produced mainly by the ovaries. Its growth is observed especially in the half-cycle in parallel with the peak of luteinizing hormone (LH), causing an increase in sexual desire [23].

On sexual performance is also affected by DHEA-S. It is an androgen produced by the adrenal cortex, derived almost exclusively from the zona reticularis, that with age undergo apoptosis. This process inevitably leads to the re-

duction of production dehydroepiandrosterone, which ultimately is converted to testosterone and dihydrotestosterone (DHT) [22]. Decline in hormone levels contributes to the development of sexual frigidity (HSDD) resulting from feeling pain during intercourse leads to disorders of sexual arousal and orgasm disorders.

According to Guay and others [22] HSDD talking about the situation of loss of libido leading as a consequence to the stress and difficulties of human relationships.

Menopause is also an increase in worsening problems with incontinence. Disruption in the production of estradiol adverse effect on the muscles and ligaments of the pelvis and the epithelium present in the birth canal and the urethra.

Rabiej and others [24] confirm that the perimenopause intensifies this indisposition.

With age, increasing the number of women suffering from pelvic genital and urinary stress incontinence [25].

Research Grodstein and others [26] show that the anatomy and function of the urinary system and sex are closely linked. Disturbances in one of these systems usually have an adverse effect on the second systems. In connective tissue, pelvic elastin content decreases, causing irreversible destruction of collagen fibers and contributes to pelvic [27].

With age, the lower urinary tract women, changes occur in reducing the flow of urine.

According to Jackson et al [28] decreases with age, the proportion between the density of the muscle fibers, and connective tissue in the pelvic floor muscles. In contrast, Melville et al [29] reported changes in muscle fiber cross-sectional sphincter muscle of the urethra, which resulted in a reduction in its cross-section.

In addition, since the third decade of life of the woman is a reduction in the amount of elastin tissue. This reduces the flexibility of pelvic. As a result of the loss of power by the collagen fibers podwieszająco-camera support is gradually stretched. Reducing the amount of elastin in the connective tissue causes the destruction of collagen fibers. This results in up to 60% decrease in the flexibility of the tissue area genital and urinary tract. The phenomenon is a slow process but it is a progressive process.

Collagen is the main component of the fascia pelvis, It combines the striated muscles of the pelvic floor of the urethra. Distinguished by different subtypes of collagen. Type I is present in the bones and tendons. while Type III is present where needed is greater flexibility for example, in venous and intestine [30,31,32,33,34,35]. It is characterized by high strength biomechanical and high flexibility. Relaxed collagen fibers wear an S-shape, only under the influence of the force are straightening. However, too much

force can cause loss of elasticity of the collagen fibers, loss of flexibility to the fascia and ligament, leading to the development of stress urinary incontinence [33,36].

The cause relaxation of the urethra and weaken its closing mechanism. They may also be psychoactive substances used in the treatment of depression [30,37].

Postmenopausal period is a time when we also observed the occurrence of abnormal uterine bleeding. Any such bleeding occurring after menopause is regarded as an irregularity to be one of the first signs of developing the disease [1].

About postmenopausal bleeding is said to be when there is 6 months or later after the cessation of menstruation. These abnormal bleeding is a major concern during menopause and their causes can be divided into organic and hormonal [7].

Among the organic causes can be distinguished fibroids, polyps neck, erosion of the vaginal part of the cervix, endometrial polyps, hyperplasia of the endometrium as well as cancers of the cervix and endometrium [38].

In the case of hormonal factors play an important role plurality of morphological changes occurring in the ovary. Reducing the number of primordial follicles, oocytes activity is reduced, the bubbles do not get full maturity, which causes the corpus luteum insufficiency. Over time, increases the number of cycles without ovulation. In the second phase of the cycle there is a deficit of progesterone secretion. The endometrium is not subject to change, menstruation does not occur. Persistent bubbles in the ovary are the reason for the excessive secretion of estrogen, occurs hyperplasia. If this phenomenon occurs repeatedly, ischaemia lining of the uterine cavity and the formation of intense bleeding chronic nature [39]. The key problem, which is relevant in the diagnostic process is to exclude organic factors, with special emphasis on their relationship oncology. To do this, perform a gynecological examination and testing of the wżniernikach, thus making assessment of the vagina and vaginal portion of the cervix. Then, perform an ultrasound to assess pelvic echostruktury uterus and endometrium, and in particular the assessment of its thickness. The study should also include a thorough assessment of the construction of the ovaries [40]. The decisive and definitive role in the diagnostic process plays a histopathological examination, excluding or confirming the cause of abnormal bleeding. The way to provide material for the study is fractional abrasion cervical and endometrial cancer. In recent years, an alternative to this study was to test hysteroscopic which combined with sonographic study increased the likelihood of accurate and rapid diagnosis [38]. The treatment is conditioned by a factor causing bleeding. In the case of large fibroids distorting the uterine muscle and disrupting its normal contractility, ultimately leading

to heavy bleeding and anemia, it is recommended to perform a hysterectomy or amputation pronouncement shaft the uterus. When using laparotomy or laparoscopy done to remove myoma intramural. Endometrial polyps and neck, submucosal fibroids and endometrial ablation is removed using a treatment hysteroscopy [41]. In the case of tumor diagnosis and apply radical surgery [38].

If organic causes are ruled out, the treatment of choice is hormone replacement therapy, tailored individually to each woman. Recommended variants of this two-component hormonal contraception, substitution of progestogen in the second phase of the cycle (16-25 days), IUD with progestogen, complex cyclic hormone therapy [7].

References

1. Bręborowicz G. Położnictwo i Ginekologia. 2006; Warszawa: PZWL.
2. Grady D. Clinical practice. Management of menopausal symptoms. *The New England Journal of Medicine*. 2006; 355: 2338-2347.
3. Sobstyl M., Bednarek W., Tkaczuk Włach J., Sobstyl J., Jakiel G. Objawy naczynioruchowe w menopauzie – diagnostyka i leczenie. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*. 2011; 3: 254 - 259.
4. Deecher DC., Dories K. Understanding the pathophysiology of vasomotor symptoms (hot flushes and night sweats) that occur in perimenopause, menopause, and postmenopause life stages. *Arch. Womens Ment. Health*. 2007; 10: 247-257.
5. Freedman RR. Physiology of hot flashes. *American Journal of Human Biology*. 2001; 13: 453-464.
6. Redberg RF., Shaw LJ. Diagnosis of coronary artery disease in women. *Progress in Cardiovascular Diseases*. 2003; 46: 239-258.
7. James DK., Jonhson RI., McEvan A. *Vademecum ginekologii*. Bielsko-Biała: 2000 – medica press.
8. Freeman EW., Sammel MD., Lin H., Gracia CR. Duration of menopausal hot flushes and associated risk factors. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2011; 117: 1095-1104.
9. Flunter ML., Mann EA. Cognitive model of menopausal hot flushes and night sweats. *Journal Psychosomatic Research*. 2010; 69: 491-501.
10. Thurston RC., Blumental JA., Babyak MA., Sherwood A. Emotional antecedents of hot flashes during daily life. *Psychosomatic Medicine*. 2005; 67.
11. Gold EB., Colvin A., Avis N., Bromberger J., Gendale GA., Powell L., et al. Longitudinal analysis of the association between vasomotor symptoms and race/ethnicity across the menopausal transition: study of women's health across the nation. *American Journal of Public Health*. 2006; 3: 122-135.
12. Crawford SL. The roles of biologic and nonbiologic factors in cultural differences in vasomotor symptoms measured by surveys. *Menopause*. 2007; 3: 725-733.
13. Thurston RC., Khoudary SR., Sutton-Tyrell K., Crandall CJ., Gold E., Sternfeld B., et al. Are vasomotor symptoms associated with alterations in hemostatic and inflammatory markers? Findings from the Study of Women's Health Across the Nation. *Menopause*. 2011; 2: 1044 - 1051.
14. Freeman EW., Sammel MD., Lin H., Gracia CR., Kappor S., Ferdousi T. The role of anxiety of hormonal changes in menopausal hot flashes. *Menopause*. 2005; 2: 258-266.
15. Crandall CJ., Tseng CH., Crawford SD., Thurston RC., Gold EB., Johnston JM., et al. Association of menopausal vasomotor symptoms with increased bone turnover during the menopausal transition *Journal of Bone Mineral Research*. 2011; 3: 840-849.
16. Rechberger T., Kulik-Rechberger B. Zmiany zanikowe w narządzie moczowo – płciowym kobiety – terapeutyczne zastosowanie estriolu. *Ginekologia po Dyplomie*. 2004; 6: 41-46.
17. Castelo-Branco C., Cancelo MJ., Villero J., Nohales F., Julia MD. Management of post-menopausal vaginal atrophy and atropic vaginitis. *Maturitas*. 2005; 52: 46-52.
18. Nyirjesy P., Leigh RD., Mathew L., Lev-Sagie A., Culhane JF. Chronic vulvovaginitis in women older than 50years: analysis of a prospective database. *The Journal of Lower Genital Tract Disease*. 2012; 16: 24-29.
19. Levine KB., Williams RE., Hartmann KE. Vulvovaginal atrophy is strongly associated with female sexual dysfunction among sexually active postmenopausal women. *Menopause*. 2008; 15: 661-666.
20. North American Menopause Society. The role of local vaginal estrogen for treatment of vaginal atrophy in postmenopausal women: 2007 position statement of The North American Menopause Society. 2007; 14: 355-369.
21. Buster JE. Seks a pięćdziesięciolatka: jak na nowo czerpać satysfakcję. *Ginekologia po Dyplomie*. 2012; 14: 70-78.
22. Guay AT., Jacobson J. Decreased freetesterosterone and dehydroepiandrosterone-sulfate (DHEA -S) levels in women with decreased libido. *Journal of Sex & Marital Therapy*. 2002; 28: 129-142.
23. Haselton MG., Mortezaie M., Pillsworth EG., Bleske-Recheck A., Frederick DA. Ovulatory shifts in human female ornamentation: near ovulation, women dress in impress. *Hormones and Behavior – Journal – Elsevier*. 2007; 51: 40-45.
24. Rabciej M., Dmoch-Gajzlerska E. Dolegliwości urologiczne u kobiet w okresie senium. *Położna Nauka i Praktyka*, 2008; 1: 46-49.
25. Fultz NH., Fisher GG., Jenkins KR. Does urinary incontinence affect middle-aged and older women's time use and activity patterns? *Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2004; 12: 1327 - 1334.
26. Grodstein F., Curhan GC. Postmenopausal hormone therapy and risk of developing urinary incontinence. *Obstetric and Gynecology*. 2004; 2: 254-260.
27. Abendstein B., Petros PE i inni. The surgical anatomy of rectocele and anterior rectal wall intussusceptio. *International Urogynecology Journal and Pelvic Floor Dysfunction*. 2008; 19: 705-710.
28. Jackson R., Vittinghoff E., Kanaya A i inni. Urinary incontinence in elderly women: findings from the Health, Aging, and Body Composition Study. *Obstetric and Gynecology*. 2004; 104: 301.
29. Melville JL., Katon W., Delaney K. Urinary incontinence in us women: apopulation-based study. *Archives Internal Medicine*. 2005; 165-537.
30. Miękoś E., Sosnowski M., Zydek C. Czynniki ryzyka występowania i zapobiegania nietrzymania moczu u kobiet. *Przegląd Menopauzalny*. 2004; 5: 43-49.
31. Chaliha C., Khullar V. Nietrzymanie moczu – epidemiologia i etiologia. *Wiadomości Położniczo-Ginekologiczne*. 2001; 1: 34-40.
32. Payal D., Patel K., Amrute V., Gopal H., Badlani S. Pelvic organ prolapse and stress urinary incontinence: A review of etiological factors. *Indian Journal of Urology*. 2007; 2: 135-141.
33. Chen Y., DeSautel M., Anderson A., Badlani G., Kushner L. Collagen synthesis is not altered in women with stress urinary incontinence. *Neurology Urodynamics*. 2004; 23: 367-373.
34. Kushner L., Mathrubutham M., Burney T., Greenwald R., Badlani G. Excretion of collagen derived peptides is increased in women with stress urinary incontinence. *Neurology Urodynamics*. 2004; 23: 198-203.

35. Chen H., Wen Y., Polan ML. Collagen metabolism and turnover in women with stress urinary incontinence and pelvic prolapse. *Int Urogynecology Journal*. 2002; 13: 80–87.
36. Goeschen K., Petros P. Uroginekologia zabiegowa w świetle Teorii Integralnej. *Anatomia czynnościowa, diagnostyka i leczenie. BiFolium*. 2009; 71–72.
37. Nygaard I., Turvey C., Burns TL. Urinary incontinence and depression in middle-aged United States women. *Obstetric & Gynecology*. 2003; 101: 149.
38. Arman F., Moerman P., Neven P., et al. Endometrial cancer. *Lancet*. 2005; 366: 491–505.
39. Montgomery BE., Daum GS., Dunton CJ. Endometrial hyperplasia: a review. *Obstetrical & Gynecological Survey*. 2004; 59: 368–378.
40. Ryan GL., Syrop CH., Van Vorhis BJ. Role, epidemiology and natural history of benign uterine mass lesions. *Clinical Gynecology and Obstetrics*. 2005; 48: 312–24.
41. Paschopoulos M., Polyzos NP., Lavasidis LG., et al. Safety issues of hysteroscopic surgery. *Am, NY Acad Sci*. 2006; 1092: 229–34.

Corresponding Author:

Jacek Kraczkowski

Email: jacek.kraczkowski@tlen.pl

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.